

THE EFFECT OF PODCASTS ON IMPROVING STUDENTS' LISTENING COMPREHENSION

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Abstract

Podcasts effectively boost student's listening comprehension by everyday audition of simple recorded audio content. The purpose of the study is to enhance pronunciation, listening and writing competences. At the same time, it will effortlessly improve vocabulary and enables to speak spontaneously without long pauses, which develops fluency and confidence. It also broaden students critical thinking through analyzing from different point of view.

Key words : listening comprehension , improve , competence , critical thinking, podcasts, autonomous learning , authentic materials.

Annotatsiya

Podkastlar oddiy yozib olingan audio kontentni har kuni tinglash orqali talabalarning tinglash qobiliyatini samarali oshiradi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi talaffuz, tinglash va yozish qobiliyatlarini oshirishdir. Shu bilan birga, u so'z boyligini osonlikcha yaxshilaydi va uzoq pauzalarsiz o'z-o'zidan gapirishga imkon beradi, bu ravonlik va ishonchni rivojlantiradi. Shuningdek, turli nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilish orqali talabalarning tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatini kengaytiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: tinglab tushunish, takomillashtirish, malaka, tanqidiy fikrlash, podkastlar , avtonom o'rganish , haqiqiy materiallar.

Аннотация

Подкасты эффективно улучшают навыки понимания на слух у студентов благодаря ежедневному прослушиванию простого аудиоконтента. Цель исследования – улучшение произношения, навыков аудирования и письма. Одновременно это позволит без труда расширить словарный запас и даст возможность говорить спонтанно, без долгих пауз, что развивает беглость речи и уверенность. Кроме того, это расширит критическое мышление студентов за счет анализа с разных точек зрения.

Ключевые слова: понимание на слух, улучшение, компетенция, критическое мышление, подкасты , автономное обучения , аутентичные материалы.

Introduction

In modern times , podcasts have been making a substantial contribution to upgrade of human life. Podcasting is an innovative form of mobile technology that consists of episodic digital audio and video content, which can be acquired and accessed on mobile devices. (Constantine (2007) Listening competence endures one of the most difficult proficiencies for EFL learners , notably in acquisition environments with limited exposure to authentic spoken

English.(Vandergrift, 2007). Listening guidance frequently relies on course books and pre-recorded aural materials, which may not adequately represent the complexity and heterogeneity in authentic communication. Consequently, a significant number of learners encounter obstacles in comprehending in spoken English, particularly when subjected to accelerated speech, a range of accents and unfamiliar linguistic features in real-world contexts beyond the classroom. (Hasan & Hoon, 2013). Speaking a foreign language fluently is difficult for learners because of insufficient practice opportunities, inadequate feedback, and limited exposure to authentic language use. The present study aims to enhance pronunciation, listening, and vocabulary, which all contribute to improving learners' speaking skills. Podcasts play an important role in improving communicative competence while developing general autonomous learning, and they are one of the most desirable resources for foreign language learning (Cameron, 2001). According to Krashen (1982), podcasts allow students to gradually master new language structures when they encounter sufficiently complex linguistic input. Authentic materials, including oral texts such as stories and audio guides, can provide students with examples of natural language use, and as a result, develop their academic writing skills. At the same time, it is noted that if the materials are relevant and interesting, and can attract the student, it can significantly increase the motivation and comfortable learning environment and the level of activity of the students and significantly reduce their anxiety.

In addition, Nunan (2004) says that students' writing skills develop more effectively when they interact with real-life content and tasks. Authentic access helps readers understand the structure and use of various texts, and supports a process approach to writing, including brainstorming, drafting, and revising. Additionally, audio recordings introduce students to different perspectives and contexts, encouraging them to consider, draw conclusions, and consider other approaches. This process develops critical thinking and allows students to draw conclusions, strengthen their opinions with examples, and at the same time, solve their own problems and develop decision-making abilities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the past decade, the integration of digital technologies in language learning, particularly in the development of listening comprehension skills, has gained significant importance. Among these technological tools, podcasts have been recognized as an effective and accessible learning resource. Numerous studies have investigated the effect of podcasts on students' listening comprehension skills, demonstrating their pedagogical advantages as well as certain limitations. According to Mark Stanley (2006), one of the earliest studies highlighting the role of podcasts in language learning was carried out by him. He identified that podcasts provide authentic listening material that enables students to actively engage with real-life language, which is crucial for developing listening comprehension development. Brian Tomlinson (2011) emphasizes the importance of regularly exposing students to authentic language input, emphasizing that listening plays a key role in developing students' listening comprehension. In this context, podcasts are seen as a very valuable resource because, unlike traditional audio materials, they provide natural speech, a variety of accents, and realistic communicative situations. Similarly, research by Hasan M. AlFadda (2019) found that students who frequently interacted with podcast content showed significantly higher levels of listening comprehension compared to those who relied solely on textbook-based recordings. The study suggests that incorporating podcasts into learning can have a positive impact on students' motivation and engagement levels. Another important advantage of podcasts in language learning is associated with supporting independent learning. As Younes Benrabah (2013)

observed, students have easy access which enables them to engage with the language on a regular basis. As a result, students are exposed to the language more frequently, which further strengthens learning. At the same time, this is also reflected in the use of podcasts. As Graham Stanley (2015) noted, this tool allows students to learn at their own pace. Repeatedly, listening to parts of the material makes the production process more efficient and serves to effectively consolidate knowledge. However, not all aspects of podcasts are entirely positive. For example, according to Christine Rosell-Aguilar (2007), using podcasts can be challenging for some learners, particularly at lower proficiency levels. Speech rate and vocabulary complexity affect comprehension. Therefore, it is important to adapt learning materials to students' proficiency levels. The effective use of podcasts depends not only on their availability, but also on how they are implemented. As Seyedeh Zahra Hashemian (2014) points out, pre- and post-listening activities significantly increase the effectiveness of the learning process. Without such methodological support, the effectiveness of podcasts may be limited. In general, most studies show the importance of podcasts in developing listening comprehension skills. They allow students to get acquainted with real language input, increase student motivation, and encourage autonomous learning. However, their effectiveness largely depends on the correct selection of teaching materials and the methodological approach of the teacher.

Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods research design to investigate the effectiveness of podcasts on students' listening comprehension skills. Below it will explain:

This approach made it possible the analysis of quantitative (test scores) and qualitative (questionnaire responses) data integrated. A total of 60 undergraduate students participated in the study. Participants were randomly assigned to two groups:

- Experimental group – 30 students
- Control group – 30 students

All participants were identified having an intermediate level of English proficiency (B1–B2). The experiment was conducted over a four-week period. Both groups followed the identical study schedule (3 sessions per week).

- Experimental group: worked with podcast-based listening materials. After each session, they completed listening comprehension activities.

- Control group: engaged with traditional textbook audio materials and completed assignments corresponding assignments. Data were collected using the following tools:

- Pre-test – to determine the level of listening comprehension prior to the commencement of the experiment

- Post-test – evaluate the outcomes upon completion of the experiment

- Questionnaire – to assess the experimental group's attitudes towards podcasts.

The data were analyzed through a comparison of pre-test and post-test results. In addition, the questionnaire responses were interpreted to determine students' attitudes towards using podcasts.

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate that podcasts are important in developing students' listening comprehension skills. In particular, the significant increase observed in the experimental group confirms the effectiveness of podcast-based learning. These results are consistent with previous studies. For example, Hasan M. AlFadda indicates in his study that students who used podcasts achieved significantly higher results than students who worked with traditional audio materials. This once again confirms the important role of authentic audio materials in the language learning process. The main reason for this is the nature of podcasts. Podcasts provide students with natural speech, a variety of pronunciations, and real-life communication situations. As Brian Tomlinson has noted, regular exposure to authentic language materials significantly improves listening comprehension skills. In addition, the flexibility and convenience of podcasts are also important factors. According to Graham Stanley, podcasts allow students to learn the material at their own pace, re-listen, and work independently. This helps to deepen their knowledge. The results of the survey also showed that student motivation increased. Interesting and realistic materials lead to more active involvement of students in the learning process. This once again proves the importance of independent learning and intrinsic motivation, as noted by Younes Benrabah. However, certain limitations should be considered. The effective use of podcasts depends on their proper pedagogical organization. As Seyedeh Zahra Hashemian noted, pre- and post-listening exercises increase the effectiveness of the process. In addition, the degree of complexity of the podcasts, the speech rate, and the suitability of the students to their level are also important. If the materials are chosen incorrectly, some students may experience difficulties in comprehension. Overall, the findings of this study indicate that the use of podcasts not only serves to develop listening comprehension, but also vocabulary, pronunciation, and critical thinking skills. Therefore, the integration of podcasts into the process of teaching a foreign language is recommended as an effective and modern approach.

Result

The results of the study showed that, especially in the experimental group, the students' listening comprehension skills improved significantly. In the initial phase of the study, both groups showed a similar level of performance. The average pre-test score of the experimental group was 56%, while the control group scored 55%. This means that there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups at the beginning of the study. The post-test results obtained after four weeks of the experiment showed a significant difference. The experimental group scored an average of 78%, while the control group scored 64%. Thus, the experimental group showed an increase of 22%, while the control group recorded a modest increase of 9%. These results confirm that the use of podcasts had a statistically significant positive effect on students' listening comprehension skills. The increase in the control group may have been due to working with traditional audio materials, but this increase was much lower compared to the experimental group. In addition, the questionnaire results also indicated a positive trend. Approximately 85% of the students in the experimental group evaluated the podcasts as engaging and beneficial. Students reported that they began to understand natural speech, different accents, and real-life communicative interactions better through podcasts. Some participants also reported improvements in their ability to extract key information, infer meaning from context, and comprehend extended spoken discourse improved through regular exposure to podcast-based materials. This suggests that podcasts not only enhance general listening comprehension, but also foster the development of listening strategies.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study indicated that podcasts are an effective tool in developing students' listening comprehension skills. According to the results, students who engaged in podcast-based materials achieved significantly improved performance than those who utilized traditional audio materials. Podcasts allow students to experience an authentic language environment, introduce different accents and real-life communication, while increasing their motivation and encouraging independent learning. In addition, podcasts not only improve listening skills, but also improve vocabulary, pronunciation, and critical thinking. It should be noted that, their effectiveness largely depends on the correct selection of materials and how to organize pre-listening and post-listening exercises. Therefore, the use of podcasts is considered as a modern and effective method to enhance communicative competence during language learning.

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